

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

The Underworld of Hydrothermal Vents

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Figure 1. View into a subsurface cavity colonized by hydrothermal vent animals and microbes observed on the R/V Falkor too expedition FKt230629.

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FKt230629
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	The Underworld of Hydrothermal Vents
Expedition Dates	2023/06/29 - 2023/07/28
Departure Port	Puntarenas, Costa Rica
Termination Port	Balboa, Panama
Ocean	South Pacific Ocean

Figure 2. Map of the expedition location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

One of the most common reproductive strategies in the Ocean is larval dispersal, a process where young animals are released into the open sea. Once eggs, sperm, or fertilized eggs develop into larvae and disperse, the open seas serve as a nursery ground. Species that spend their life on the seafloor will settle as they mature in their juvenile and adult stages. Some animals, like corals or tubeworms, adhere themselves to rocks. Dispersal and settlement are important biological mechanisms for maintaining genetic diversity in the Ocean, where ocean circulation patterns help ensure new areas are colonized and the genetic health of the population is maintained. While these processes are well-studied in coastal environments, there is not as much research on dispersal and settlement in the deep sea, especially for hydrothermal vent communities.

Hydrothermal vents are dynamic ecosystems that are also prone to regular disturbances, like volcanic eruptions and earthquakes. Some hydrothermal vents have brief lifespans, yet, wherever one forms, a biological community almost always follows, and how these animals arrive was not confirmed. Further, while scientists had plentiful evidence that hydrothermal animals reproduce and the animal larvae live around hydrothermal vents, the presence of tubeworm larvae had not been found around the vents, which might suggest a dispersal mechanism beyond open Ocean circulation patterns.

This expedition set out to discover, observe, and document the diversity of life living beneath deep-sea hydrothermal vents. The research team suspected that larvae were being sucked into and pumped out of cracks in the surrounding seafloor, and that this passage through the subseafloor could facilitate the right conditions for spreading animal larvae and adults, and microbial communities between vent fields.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

The expedition was in international waters. For import and export of samples to and from Panama permits were granted to Monika Bright, Sabine Gollner and Jessica Mitchell.

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition commenced on June 29, 2023, departing from Puntarenas, Costa Rica, and ended in Balboa, Panama, on July 28, 2023.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

The expedition had three main objectives: to describe biosphere diversity beneath deep-sea hydrothermal vents from microbe to animal level, clarify the nature and extent of connectivity between biospheres at and below vents as well as non-vent systems, and test the hypothesis that the larvae of some species living at hydrothermal vents travel through vent fluid in subsurface environments to colonize new vent structures.

The team aimed to attach an in situ mass spectrometer, a device for measuring molecules and isotopes, to ROV *SuBastian*. Due to failure of this equipment, the scientists used ROV sensors as well as fluid samples to create environmental and chemical profiles of the subseafloor around

the vents. The team also collected rock, fluid, and animal samples from the vent and non-vent surfaces and rock, fluid, and animal samples from the subsurface, using ROV *SuBastian's* pumps and robotic arms.

In conjunction with the core project, several other projects were carried out, to better understand: 1) The physiology of the facultative symbionts of the giant tubeworm *Riftia pachyptila* and the mussel *Bathymodiolus thermophilis*, 2) The limits of thermotolerance of various vent animals, 3) The reproductive cycle in hydrothermal vent Polynoidae, 4) Gastropod symbiosis, 5) Microbial metabolic activity in sample incubations from different modes of hydrothermal venting, 6) Particles as platforms for microbial communities. 7) Viral production, and 8) Molluscan living and death assemblages at deep-sea hydrothermal vents.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Science

The research team deployed several experiments, including a newly designed mesh box–staining gadget used at tubeworm clumps to study which animals and microbes are flushed out from the subsurface. Initial experiments failed to reveal life beneath the surface and, so, pilots used ROV *SuBastian's* manipulators to break open and overturn a section of the seafloor. When the rocky substrate was overturned, cavities of lobate lava packed with worms, snails, and chemosynthetic bacteria living in the 23.9 degrees Celsius water were revealed. The team proved that two dynamic vent habitats exist; vent animals above and below the surface thrive together in unison, both depending on vent fluid from below and oxygen in the seawater from above.

Analysis of samples collected from above and below the vents will allow the scientists to assess the connection between these communities. Ultimately, this discovery transforms the scientific understanding of ecology and evolution of animal life at and beneath hydrothermal vents in the deep sea.

The expedition consisted of 17 ROV dives in an area located on the East Pacific Rise (9°50' N, 104°17' W) at the axial summit trough in about 2500 m water depth, one of the most well-studied deep-sea hydrothermal vent areas located on a fast spreading ridge. The core project was executed at a new site, called **Fava Flow Suburbs** (Figure 3, Table 1). One ROV dive was done at 9°53' N, 105°43' W, 3.1 km off-axis in order to sample sediments to compare communities with vent and subvent communities.

All together, 220 ROV samples were shared among the scientists, which led to a total number of 2,509 subsamples. On average, each ROV sample led to an average of 11.5 subsamples/ROV sample (see Appendix 3.1).

Figure 3. Photograph of Fava Flow Suburbs with six Experimental Sites

2.2 Post-Expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

The discovery of a subsurface habitat colonized by animals and microbes in small cavities beneath the seafloor has further prompted the scientists to investigate the connectivity of animal and microbial communities between surface and subsurface hydrothermal vents and the surrounding non-vent surface areas.

The time dedicated to the core project was extended due to the discovery of animal life in subsurface vents below the surface (Bright et al. 2024). A broad sampling scheme of seawater, vent fluid, rocks, and microbial and animal communities above and below vents will allow the science team to assess the connection between these two communities by morphological identification of animals (meiofauna and macrofauna) and molecular identification of smaller organisms (Bacteria, Archaea, Fungi, Eukaryotes).

Abiotic parameters were measured in situ and from water samples collected at six selected sites (designated Experiments 1-6) at Fava Flow Suburbs (Bright et al. 2024). Five cavities were inhabited by animals, and these exhibited a maximum temperature of 18.1 ± 7.1 °C (mean \pm standard deviation). Temperatures in the cavities and among tubeworms and mussels on the seafloor surface were similar, but significantly different for vent surface habitats and ambient temperatures, and subsurface habitat and ambient temperatures. The abiotic conditions inside the cavities, had a temperature of 18.1 ± 7.1 °C, a pH 6.1 ± 0.4 , a salinity 33.8 ± 0.4 , a minimum concentration of 136 ± 165 μmolL^{-1} H₂S [i.e., sum of all forms of dissolved sulfide], and

maximum $63 \pm 25 \mu\text{molL}^{-1}$ oxygen concentrations (Table 1, Bright et al. 2024), and were all well within the range of the temporally variable conditions measured at the surface among animal clumps as well as previously found in tubeworm clumps.

ROV recovery dive #	S0552	S0554	S0556	S0557	S0558	S0560
Date	13.07.23	15.07.23	17.07.23	18.07.23	19.07.23	21.07.23
Longitude	9.840237	9.840121	9.840075	9.840133	9.840238	9.840108
Latitude	-104.291860	-104.291860	-104.291812	-104.291874	-104.292038	-104.291805
Depth (m)	2515	2515	2515	2515	2512	2515
Ambient T (°C)	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.0	2.0	2.1
Ambient salinity	34.7	34.7	34.7	34.7	34.7	34.7
Ambient oxygen ($\Sigma\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	107	106	105	106	105	N/A
Surface max. T (°C)	19.7	10.4	22.7	2.1	9.5	9.1
Subseafloor max. T (°C)	24.9	24.0	24.9	11.6	7.0	10.0
Subs. salinity	33.8	34.0	33.3	34.0	34.4	33.8
Subs. pH	6.4	5.7	5.5	6.5	6.5	6.2
Subs. min. H ₂ S ($\Sigma\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	N/A	197	401	14	20	25
Subs. max. oxygen ($\Sigma\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	N/A	N/A	50	91	115	47
Lava shelf thickness (cm)	10	12	11	15	10	12
Lava plate surface (m ²)	0.13	0.21	0.24	0.08	0.07	0.06
Cavity height (cm)	10	10	10	10	5	10

Table 1: Excavation into crustal subseafloor hydrothermal vents at Fava Flow Suburbs at 9°50'N EPR Region in 2023.

Seawater, vent fluid, rocks, and animal communities from the six sites (Experiments 1-6) were sampled with grab, suction or blue bag and stored in 96% ethanol at -20°C until processing on shore to obtain **macro- and meiofaunal communities** (see Table 2 and Table 3 in the Appendix for a complete overview of the samples and analyses status).

A morphology-based approach was applied for taxonomic assignment to the lowest taxonomic rank (whenever possible), based on Desbryuères et al. (2006), Mills et al. (2009) and original species descriptions. Sorting and identification of macrofauna is complete; meiofauna samples are currently being processed and expected to be completed in October 2025. Table 4 in the Appendix contains preliminary abundance data per sample and habitat for ~17300 specimens processed so far (updated 04.07.2025). Preparation of microscope slides, required for the identification of permanent meiofauna (Copepoda and Nematoda) is ongoing.

Barcoding is ongoing for individuals with limited morphological identification characteristics due to high phenotypic variation between taxa, early-life stages, or unknown taxa (Table 5). Abundance matrices for each taxon and sample will be used as input for analyses of community composition, diversity indices and multivariate statistics in Rstudio (R Core Team, 2024). Selected species will be used to investigate connectivity patterns by applying population genomic analyses using 2bRAD approaches.

Preliminary analyses on the macrofauna component revealed 67 taxa among ~ 4000 specimens. All the taxa observed in the subseafloor habitat have already been reported from specimens living the surface of the seafloor (no new species described so far), supporting the similarity between the environments. The subseafloor habitat yields higher diversity than the above surface as well as a more balanced abundance of different taxa. As expected, macrofauna communities in the diffuse vent habitats (surface and subseafloor) are significantly different from the communities found on bare basalt. Preliminary results of the meiofauna reveal a high proportion of non-permanent meiofauna (larval and juvenile stages of Gastropoda and Polychaeta macrofaunal species) in the subseafloor habitats, supporting the idea of successful reproduction taking place in this habitat. Regarding permanent meiofauna, preliminary data suggest that nematodes dominate surface habitats, whereas copepods are more abundant in the subseafloor.

The results of these analyses show that the subseafloor harbors vent-endemic macro- and meiofauna at all life-stages, including larvae, supporting the hypothesis of larval dispersal through the subseafloor and the finding that adult vent-fauna can live in subseafloor cavities. These new findings may help emphasize the need for considering protections for vent habitats, as many details of these habitats are still being learned and discovered.

The **microbial communities** were sampled by filtering seawater using swabs from the same samples as the animal as the animal communities (Table 5). Full length amplicon sequencing of 16S, 18S and ITS aims to explore microbial communities of Bacteria and Archaea, Eukaryota and Fungi, respectively. A full overview of the samples and current status of the microbial community analyses is shown in Table 5: sequencing is completed for 16S Bacteria and ongoing for the remaining markers; bacterial community data is currently being analyzed.

Preliminary results suggest that bacterial communities are different among habitats (subseafloor, surface or basalt), even when comparing subseafloor and surface samples from the same experiment and site. Subseafloor communities are more diverse than the surface counterparts, and only 67 of the 208 amplicon sequence variants (ASV) detected in this habitat are shared with the surface, highlighting the uniqueness of the subseafloor habitat. Out of the total 404 ASVs, only 38 are shared among the three habitats. In the subseafloor, sulfur-oxidizing and carbon-fixing Campylobacteria dominate the bacterial assemblages. On the other hand, the surface is dominated by Campylobacteria and Gammaproteobacteria at similar contribution levels. Up to 59% of the taxa are rare contributors for the overall bacterial diversity, with less than 1% relative abundance. Different bacterial assemblages are targeted with water filter or swab samples, as expected from the experimental design.

Preliminary analyses highlight that microbial communities in the subseafloor are distinct from surface communities.

Associated Projects

1) Physiology of the facultative symbionts of the giant tubeworm *Riftia pachyptila* and the mussel *Bathymodiolus thermophilus* (Monika Bright, Teresa Winter, Ingrid Kolar, Philipp Prötz, André Luiz de Oliveira, Salvador Manuel Espada-Hinojosa, Antonia Auer)

In both symbioses (*Riftia pachyptila*, *Bathymodiolus thermophilus*), transmission of their sulfur-oxidizing chemotrophic symbionts is horizontal. The facultative, free-living symbionts infect each host generation anew. When the tubeworms die, part of the host-associated symbiont population escapes the dead host. To better understand the physiology of the free-living symbiont, host death was simulated and the free-living symbionts were incubated under various environmental conditions. Mainly, the science team was interested in investigating the potential heterotrophic metabolism of the symbiont. Upon incubations in high-pressure vessels (26 tubeworm experiments, 16 mussel experiments), samples were frozen for transcriptome sequencing and analyses. All tubeworm symbiont samples have been sequenced and are currently being analyzed. The mussel symbiont samples still await sequencing.

2) Limits of thermotolerance of various vent animals (Alessandro Messori, Sabine Gollner)

Specimens for thermotolerance experiments were mainly collected at Tica vent in two different habitats: focused flow/Pompeii worm aggregations and diffuse flow/tubeworm & mussel aggregations. Dirivultid copepods were randomly selected for each of the 118 incubations performed in different temperature, oxygen, and pressure conditions. All copepods that died during incubations were stored in ethanol for taxonomic identification following their original species descriptions. Primary data are published [here](#). The data analysis produced a generalized relation between exposure time and median lethal temperature in dirivultid copepod communities from the sampled habitats through a combination of nonlinear least squares regression and linear regression. Forthcoming results will describe the physiological limits of a vent meiofauna community and shed light on how the turbulent conditions of these habitats are experienced at a small scale and how a combination of physiology, competition, and habitat structure may influence colonization and succession.

3) Reproductive cycle in hydrothermal vent Polynoidae (Stephane Hourdez)

Deep-sea hydrothermal vent scale-worms (Annelida; Polynoidae) are diverse, with about nine species on the East Pacific Rise. Our work indicates that in all the samples from previous cruises we studied, there are mature oocytes present. This observation of continuous reproduction may be biased because cruises most often take place in November-March, when the weather conditions are best for diving with submersibles. During this cruise, we collected all nine of the common species and will study their reproductive state in the laboratory. These data will be added to earlier measurements and observations.

4) Gastropod symbiosis (Ian Hughes)

Gastropods in the order Neomphalida were collected live during the expedition, primarily using the suction sampler aboard ROV *SuBastian*. For species where more than eight individuals were recovered alive, gastropods were incubated with isotopically labeled bicarbonate using the Girguis Lab High Pressure Respirometry System to examine carbon fixation through potential symbiosis. Other individuals were preserved in ethanol, RNA later, or

flash frozen in liquid nitrogen for morphological and DNA-based analysis. Bulk isotope analysis of associate incubation revealed high levels of inorganic carbon incorporation in the neomphalid gastropod *Cyathernia naticoides*, however, other species collected from the same locality, such as *Rhynchopelta concentrica*, showed no evidence of inorganic carbon incorporation under experimental conditions, supporting the suggestion that *Rhynchopelta* are aposymbiotic. Combined with samples from museum collections and additional expeditions, we currently have representatives of 20 of the ~25 genera in the gastropod order Neomphalida, and plan to use phylogenomic tools to construct a phylogeny of this lineage and examine the evolution of symbiosis in this group.

In addition to Neomphaliones gastropods, limpets in the genus *Lepetodrilus* were also collected and preserved for DNA analysis (either flash frozen or in RNA later) as part of a larger project on potential phyllosymbiosis in *Lepetodrilus* limpets. The microbial communities associated with samples collected on this cruise will be compared with those of *Lepetodrilus* limpets from other vent communities, including Juan de Fuca and the Mid-Atlantic Ridge.

5) Microbial metabolic activity in sample incubations from different modes of hydrothermal venting (Avery Fulford)

Samples were taken of hydrothermal vent chimney chunks and non-hydrothermal seafloor basalt using *SuBastian's* hydraulic arm. Additionally, chimney sections were sectioned into distinct mineralogical layers along their horizontal gradient, and individual chimney layers and basalt chips were homogenized using a sterilized hammer or mortar and pestle. Diffuse-flow hydrothermal venting and ambient seawater were pumped into a collection bag and filtered aboard the ship. Samples were split, so that half of each chimney, basalt, diffuse-flow fluid, or ambient seawater sample was either submerged in Glycerol TE buffer before freezing at -80°C, or frozen immediately at -80°C without buffer.

Samples collected during the cruise are being processed and will be used to compare microbial activity and metabolism with similar samples collected from a brine-dominated hydrothermal vent system. While most studies examining microbial composition and function at hydrothermal vents have focused on the vapor-dominated phase of venting, characterized by volatile-rich fluids, much less is known about microbes at brine-dominated vents. This style of venting occurs when phase separation in the lithosphere causes dense, high-salinity brines to accumulate in subseafloor reservoirs. These systems are enriched in heavy metals such as Fe(II) and Mn(II) due to their long residence in the subsurface.

Samples collected from this cruise—as well as from brine-dominated vents, collected separately—that were frozen immediately at -80°C without buffer, will be subjected to DNA extraction and 16S amplicon sequencing to determine the taxonomic identity of samples. Next, samples preserved in Glycerol TE buffer before freezing will be used for incubations to compare microbial metabolic activity between these different modes of hydrothermal venting. Samples will be enriched under simulated in situ conditions to promote a key microbial metabolism, then homogenized and incubated in parallel to assess metabolic rates between sample types. After incubations, metagenomic analyses of the incubated samples will confirm the taxonomic, metabolic, and genomic signatures of the microbial communities studied.

6) Particles as platforms for microbial communities (Clarissa Karthäuser, Stefan M. Sievert)

Particles suspended in the vent surrounding, outflow, hydrothermal plume and the overlying water column were collected by *SuBastian* using Niskin bottles and a bag filled by a pump. A microscopic image (Figure 4) was taken of each of the 396 individual particle, after which 362 particles and background water samples were incubated to determine oxygen consumption using a newly built robotic incubator (RotoBOD, Figure 5). Incubations were amended with stable isotopes to test for autotrophy and nitrogen cycling. Subsequently, particles were either preserved in Ethanol for visualization coupled to element analysis (SEM/EDX, 157 samples), or frozen for DNA extractions (311 samples). Using a correlative approach, we hope to determine sources and ecosystem functions of particle-associated microbial communities in the deep sea and specifically near hydrothermal vents based on these measurements.

Figure 4. Exemplary microscopic images of particles collected throughout the water column and at vents.

Figure 5. The RotoBOD, a new device for monitoring oxygen concentrations in rotating small samples.

Respiration data obtained during the cruise were analyzed, revealing low respiration rates in deep-sea particles, but higher respiration compared with particles from the overlying water column that were incubated under the same conditions. Further analyses (SEM/EDS and genetic analyses) are currently underway. Preliminary results revealed some relevant connections between water column carbon export and sequestration in the deep sea, which need to be studied in more detail.

7) Viral production (Christian Winter, Tinkara Tinta, Nicole Krause)

Virus experiments were carried out under in situ pressure in high pressure vessels and under surface pressure conditions in parallel. These experiments were based on the virus-dilution approach to measure virus production rates directly and determine the frequency of virally-infected prokaryotic cells in the retrieved water samples by using the prokaryotic fraction and virus-free water obtained from the same water mass as the growth medium. Currently, the results of these data are being analyzed. Primary data are published [here](#).

8) Molluscan living and death assemblages at deep-sea hydrothermal vents (Jan Steger)

The emerging field of conservation paleobiology is increasingly capitalizing on death assemblages – the time-averaged accumulations of durable, taxonomically identifiable organismal remains encountered on the seafloor (e.g., molluscan shells) – to gain information on the long-term states, past compositional changes, and metacommunity diversity of marine benthic assemblages. However, the properties of death assemblages in deep-sea habitats remain poorly understood despite increasing anthropogenic pressures, including plans to industrially mine hydrothermally deposited sulfidic ores. To address this knowledge gap, vent-associated molluscan living and death assemblages were sampled from a range of microhabitats at the East Pacific Rise, 9°50'N, such as active chimney walls and their bases, live mixed tubeworm *Riftia pachyptila* and mussel *Bathymodiolus thermophilus* aggregations, a dead mussel bed, and peripheral bare basalt. As the presence and accumulation of biogenic carbonates depends not only input rates (shell production) and local environmental conditions (e.g., carbonate saturation state, bioturbation), but also shell traits such as thickness, organic content, crystal ultrastructure and mineralogy, a wide array of bivalve and gastropod species were collected for analysis at the University of Vienna (Austria) and the Senckenberg Research Institute and Natural History

Museum Frankfurt (SMF; Germany). Preliminary screening and partial sorting of living and death assemblages from bulk samples from Tica vent field revealed only a small number of empty molluscan shells compared to the high abundance of live-collected individuals, in line with previous reports of rapid dissolution of such remains in the acidic environment at and near active hydrothermal vents. More detailed analyses and comparisons of living and death assemblages are planned upon final sorting and identification of the remaining samples. Finally, voucher specimens of various invertebrate taxa (Mollusca, Annelida, Crustacea) were collected for research and teaching purposes, such as exhibitions, student courses, and outreach activities at SMF.

Figure 6. - left. An empty and taphonomically altered shell of *Turnerconcha magnifica* (Boss & Turner, 1980) being collected by the manipulator arm of ROV SuBastian (sampling event S0555_140); right: Suction sampling on bare basalt in the periphery of Tica Field to collect living mollusks and any empty shells (sampling event S0557_172).

2.2.2 New Discoveries

For the first time, small, shallow caves in the subsurface of the deep sea were discovered. These cavities of lobate lava below hydrothermal vents at the vent site Fava Flow Suburbs are inhabited by sessile tubeworms and mobile vent animals. Our previous understanding of animal life at deep-sea hydrothermal vents at the surface of the Earth's crust gets, with this discovery, another dimension, the shallow subsurface in the crust. Two dynamic vent habitats exist, and vent animals above and below the surface thrive together in unison, both depending on vent fluid from below and oxygen in the seawater from above.

In addition, a broad sampling scheme of sea water, vent fluid, rocks, and microbial and animal communities above and below vents will enable the assessment of the connection between these two communities upon sequencing in the upcoming months.

2.2.3 Software Utilized

- Rstudio (R Core Team, 2024) and R packages: clustsig (Whitaker and Christman, 2014); vegan (Oksanen *et al.*, 2024), future (Bengtsson, 2021), iNEXT (Chao *et al.*, 2014), pairwiseAdonis (Arbizu, 2017)
- Whitaker D, Christman M (2014). *_clustsig: Significant Cluster Analysis_*. R package version 1.1, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=clustsig>

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- Chao, A., Gotelli, N. J., Hsieh, T. C., Sander, E. L., Ma, K. H., Colwell, R. K., and Ellison, A. M. 2014. Rarefaction and extrapolation with Hill numbers: a framework for sampling and estimation in species diversity studies. *Ecological Monographs* 84:45-67
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- Chromatograms and raw sequences were reviewed with BioEdit v.7.0.5.3 (Hall, 1999) Hall, T.A., 1999. BioEdit: a user-friendly biological sequence alignment editor and analysis program for Windows 95/98/NT. *Nucleic Acids Symp Ser* 41, 95–98.
- Presence stop codons and pseudogenes was verified with ExPASy Translate Tool.
- ExPASy Translate Tool accessed January 2022 <https://web.expasy.org/translate/>.

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date.

Data Type	Curator	Status
Vessel underway data (CTD, Multibeam sonar, etc.)	Rolling Deck to Repository	Completed
ADCP Data	University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Completed
Data collected by ROV <i>SuBastian</i> , including navigation, acoustic backscatter, conductivity, oxygen, temperature, and photography	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
Currently accepted taxa	World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) .	In-Progress
Lethal Time 50 experiment results	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO)	Completed
In situ prokaryotic and viral abundance from hydrothermal vent site Tica samples	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO)	
Physico-chemical habitat characterization	Bright et al. 2024	Completed

Data Type	Curator	Status
Prokaryotic and viral abundances	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO)	Completed
Animal Diversity and Community		In-progress
Animal population genetic analysis		In-progress
Microbes taxonomy from genetic sequence		In-progress
Animal taxonomy from larvae		In-progress
Microbial diversity and community		In-progress
Animal Taxonomy from light microscopy analysis		In-progress
Virus Production at Hydrothermal Vents		In-progress
Surface and subsurface vent fluid and bottom water samples		In-progress

2.4 Publications

Bright, M., Gollner, S., de Oliveira, A., Espada-Hinojose, S. Fulford, A., Vincent Hughes, I., et al. (2024). Animal life in the shallow subseafloor crust at deep-sea hydrothermal vents. *Nature Comms.* 15, 8466. doi: 10.1038/s41467-024-52631-9.

3 Appendix

3.1 Collected Samples

Table 2. Overview of selected faunal samples for analyses of community composition collected during the research cruise. The current sorting/analyses process is presented in the columns MA (macrofauna community) and ME (meiofauna community) and are labeled green if analyzed and orange if ongoing (at the time of report publication). Details on location and sampling are also provided.

Dive	Sample ID	DateTimeStamp	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)	Sub sample ID	Site Name	MA	ME
S0543	S0543_001	2023-07-04T17:55:34.910Z	9,8403	-104,2919	2517,08	SG001	other		
S0543	S0543_002	2023-07-04T19:06:51.084Z	9,8403	-104,2919	2517,1	SG002	other		
S0543	S0543_002	2023-07-04T19:06:51.084Z	9,8403	-104,2919	2517,1	SG003	other		
S0544	S0544_010	2023-07-05T16:10:22.529Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,24	SG013	EX1		
S0544	S0544_014	2023-07-05T17:15:58.278Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,48	SG014	EX1		
S0544	S0544_014	2023-07-05T17:15:58.278Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,48	SG015	EX1		
S0544	S0544_015	2023-07-05T17:50:45.028Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,46	SG016	EX1		
S0544	S0544_015	2023-07-05T17:50:45.028Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,46	SG017	EX1		

Dive	Sample ID	DateTimeStamp	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)	Sub sample ID	Site Name	MA	ME
S0546	S0546_025	2023-07-07T16:48:25.294Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2518,14	SG030	EX2		
S0546	S0546_026	2023-07-07T18:04:16.587Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2518,36	SG031	EX2		
S0546	S0546_026	2023-07-07T18:04:16.587Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2518,36	SG032	EX2		
S0546	S0546_026	2023-07-07T18:04:16.587Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2518,36	SG033	EX2		
S0546	S0546_026	2023-07-07T18:04:16.587Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2518,36	SG034	EX2		
S0546	S0546_026	2023-07-07T18:04:16.587Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2518,36	SG035	EX2		
S0546	S0546_027	2023-07-07T19:33:47.349Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2518,28	SG036	EX2		
S0546	S0546_027	2023-07-07T19:33:47.349Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2518,28	SG037	EX2		
S0546	S0546_028	2023-07-07T19:50:34.927Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2518,25	SG038	EX2		
S0546	S0546_028	2023-07-07T19:50:34.927Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2518,25	SG039	EX2		
S0546	S0546_029	2023-07-07T20:24:40.925Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2518,39	SG040	EX2		
S0546	S0546_029	2023-07-07T20:24:40.925Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2518,39	SG041	EX2		
S0548	S0548_038	2023-07-09T16:56:17.709Z	9,8401	-104,2917	2515,45	SG045	EX3		
S0548	S0548_039	2023-07-09T18:13:16.156Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,52	SG046	EX3		
S0548	S0548_039	2023-07-09T18:13:16.156Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,52	SG047	EX3		
S0548	S0548_040	2023-07-09T18:59:31.925Z	9,8401	-104,2917	2515,35	SG048	EX3		
S0548	S0548_040	2023-07-09T18:59:31.925Z	9,8401	-104,2917	2515,35	SG049	EX3		
S0550	S0550_055	2023-07-11T16:12:19.239Z	9,8402	-104,2917	2514,12	SG058	other		
S0550	S0550_056	2023-07-11T17:19:05.122Z	9,8402	-104,2917	2514,22	SG059	other		
S0550	S0550_056	2023-07-11T17:19:05.122Z	9,8402	-104,2917	2514,22	SG060	other		
S0550	S0550_058	2023-07-11T17:44:07.759Z	9,8402	-104,2917	2514,11	SG061	other		
S0550	S0550_059	2023-07-11T17:49:46.664Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,06	SG062	other		
S0550	S0550_059	2023-07-11T17:49:46.664Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,06	SG063	other		
S0550	S0550_060	2023-07-11T18:00:42.552Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2513,95	SG064	other		
S0550	S0550_060	2023-07-11T18:00:42.552Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2513,95	SG065	other		
S0552	S0552_088	2023-07-13T16:58:08.481Z	9,8402	-104,2919	2514,3	SG070	EX1		
S0552	S0552_088	2023-07-13T16:58:08.481Z	9,8402	-104,2919	2514,3	SG078	EX1		
S0552	S0552_090	2023-07-13T18:23:35.317Z	9,8402	-104,2919	2514,35	SG079	EX1		
S0552	S0552_090	2023-07-13T18:23:35.317Z	9,8402	-104,2919	2514,35	SG080	EX1		
S0553	S0553_097	2023-07-14T17:57:01.214Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,32	SG083	EX1		
S0553	S0553_101	2023-07-14T18:58:56.439Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,32	SG084	EX1		
S0553	S0553_102	2023-07-14T19:06:29.426Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,31	SG085	EX1		
S0553	S0553_103	2023-07-14T19:12:43.089Z	9,8402	-104,2919	2514,3	SG086	EX1		
S0553	S0553_104	2023-07-14T19:25:45.687Z	9,8402	-104,2919	2514,37	SG087	EX1		
S0554	S0554_118	2023-07-15T19:39:36.550Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2514,09	SG139	EX2		
S0554	S0554_119	2023-07-15T20:23:52.483Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2513,98	SG140	EX2		
S0554	S0554_119	2023-07-15T20:23:52.483Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2513,98	SG141	EX2		
S0554	S0554_120	2023-07-15T20:35:57.553Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,02	SG144	EX2		
S0554	S0554_120	2023-07-15T20:35:57.553Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2514,02	SG145	EX2		
S0555	S0555_131	2023-07-16T16:43:26.751Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,31	SG146	EX2		
S0555	S0555_139	2023-07-16T19:56:54.224Z	9,8402	-104,2919	2511,28	SG153	other		

Dive	Sample ID	DateTimeStamp	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)	Sub sample ID	Site Name	MA	ME
S0556	S0556_152	2023-07-17T16:48:48.202Z	9,8401	-104,2917	2516,22	SG163	EX3		
S0556	S0556_154	2023-07-17T18:30:05.005Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,8	SG164	EX3		
S0556	S0556_155	2023-07-17T19:45:00.000Z	9,8401	104,29179	2515,41	SG165	EX3		
S0556	S0556_155	2023-07-17T19:45:00.000Z	9,8401	104,29179	2515,41	SG166	EX3		
S0556	S0556_157	2023-07-17T20:29:35.607Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,21	SG167	EX1		
S0556	S0556_157	2023-07-17T20:29:35.607Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,21	SG168	EX2		
S0556	S0556_154	2023-07-17T18:30:05.005Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,8	SG169	EX3		
S0557	S0557_168	2023-07-18T18:25:30.496Z	9,8401	-104,2919	2515,11	SG170	EX4		
S0556	S0556_156	2023-07-17T20:24:25.003Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,37	SG171	EX3		
S0556	S0556_156	2023-07-17T20:24:25.003Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,37	SG172	EX3		
S0557	S0557_163	2023-07-18T15:43:33.701Z	9,8401	-104,2919	2515,52	SG173	EX4		
S0557	S0557_163	2023-07-18T15:43:33.701Z	9,8401	-104,2919	2515,52	SG174	EX4		
S0557	S0557_164	2023-07-18T15:44:30.905Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2515,59	SG175	EX4		
S0557	S0557_165	2023-07-18T16:25:09.823Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,41	SG176	EX4		
S0557	S0557_166	2023-07-18T17:35:52.567Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,44	SG177	EX4		
S0557	S0557_166	2023-07-18T17:35:52.567Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,44	SG178	EX4		
S0557	S0557_169	2023-07-18T18:51:56.983Z	9,8401	-104,2919	2515,23	SG179	EX4		
S0558	S0558_180	2023-07-19T15:11:24.302Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2516,14	SG183	EX5		
S0558	S0558_181	2023-07-19T18:52:15.238Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2516,04	SG184	EX5		
S0558	S0558_182	2023-07-19T20:06:44.509Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2515,92	SG185	EX5		
S0558	S0558_182	2023-07-19T20:06:44.509Z	9,8402	-104,2918	2515,92	SG186	EX5		
S0560	S0560_206	2023-07-21T12:38:15.297Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,02	SG197	EX6		
S0560	S0560_206	2023-07-21T12:38:15.297Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,02	SG198	EX6		
S0560	S0560_208	2023-07-21T13:19:39.859Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2514,98	SG199	EX6		
S0560	S0560_208	2023-07-21T13:19:39.859Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2514,98	SG200	EX6		
S0560	S0560_209	2023-07-21T14:28:00.515Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,01	SG201	EX6		
S0560	S0560_210	2023-07-21T15:32:58.162Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2517,57	SG202	EX6		
S0560	S0560_211	2023-07-21T16:19:19.522Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,52	SG203	EX6		
S0560	S0560_211	2023-07-21T16:19:19.522Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2515,52	SG204	EX6		
S0560	S0560_207	2023-07-21T12:56:58.853Z	9,8401	-104,2918	2514,97	SG210	EX6		

Table 3. Overview of selected fauna samples per experiment (1-6). Details on sampling method, habitat (surface, seafloor, basalt), and foundation species at the surface (tubeworms TW, mussels M, NA) are also provided.

Sub Sample ID	Site	Area sampled (m ²)	Sampling method	Habitat	Foundation species at the surface
SG013	EX1	0,16	Blue bag above vent	Surface	TW
SG014	EX1	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW
SG015	EX1	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW

Sub Sample ID	Site	Area sampled (m ²)	Sampling method	Habitat	Foundation species at the surface
SG016	EX1	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW
SG017	EX1	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW
SG079	EX1	0,13	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW
SG080	EX1	0,13	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW
SG083	EX1	0,13	Blue bag underworld	Subseafloor	TW
SG084	EX1	0,13	Slurp ultrafine net	Subseafloor	TW
SG085	EX1	0,13	Slurp fine net	Subseafloor	TW
SG086	EX1	0,13	Slurp large net	Subseafloor	TW
SG087	EX1	0,13	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW
SG001	EX1	0,16	Blue bag above basalt	Basalt	NA
SG002	EX1	0,16	Bare basalt rock	Basalt	NA
SG003	EX1	0,16	Bare basalt rock	Basalt	NA
SG030	EX2	0,16	Blue bag above vent	Surface	TW + M
SG031	EX2	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG032	EX2	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG033	EX2	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG034	EX2	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG035	EX2	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG036	EX2	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG037	EX2	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG038	EX2	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG039	EX2	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG040	EX2	0,16	Rocks	Surface	TW + M
SG041	EX2	0,16	Rocks	Surface	TW + M
SG126	EX2	0,21	Limpets	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG139	EX2	0,21	Suction fine	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG140	EX2	0,21	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG141	EX2	0,21	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG144	EX2	0,21	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG145	EX2	0,21	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG146	EX2	0,21	Blue bag	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG058	EX2	0,16	Blue bag above basalt	Basalt	NA
SG059	EX2	0,16	Bare basalt rock	Basalt	NA
SG060	EX2	0,16	Bare basalt rock	Basalt	NA

Sub Sample ID	Site	Area sampled (m ²)	Sampling method	Habitat	Foundation species at the surface
SG061	EX2	0,16	Suction ultrafine	Basalt	NA
SG062	EX2	0,16	Suction fine	Basalt	NA
SG062	EX2	0,16	Suction fine	Basalt	NA
SG064	EX2	0,16	Suction large	Basalt	NA
SG065	EX2	0,16	Suction large	Basalt	NA
SG126	EX2	0,21	limpets from underworld	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG045	EX3	0,16	Blue bag above vent	Surface	TW + M
SG046	EX3	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG047	EX3	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG048	EX3	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG049	EX3	0,16	Suction at tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG163	EX3	0,24	Blue bag	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG164	EX3	0,24	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG165	EX3	0,24	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG166	EX3	0,24	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG167	EX3	0,24	Grab of tubeworms	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG168	EX3	0,24	Grab of tubeworms	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG169	EX3	0,24	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG171	EX3	0,24	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG172	EX3	0,24	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG153	EX3	0,16	Bare basalt rock	Basalt	NA
SG173	EX4	0,16	Suction ultrafine	Surface	TW + M
SG174	EX4	0,16	Suction ultrafine	Surface	TW + M
SG175	EX4	0,16	Grab of tubeworms	Surface	TW + M
SG170	EX4	0,08	Rocks	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG176	EX4	0,08	Blue bag	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG177	EX4	0,08	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG178	EX4	0,08	Suction	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG179	EX4	0,08	Suction ultrafine	Subseafloor	TW + M
SG183	EX5	0,16	Suction	Surface	M
SG184	EX5	0,07	Blue bag	Subseafloor	M
SG185	EX5	0,07	Rocks	Subseafloor	M
SG186	EX5	0,07	Rocks	Subseafloor	M

Sub Sample ID	Site	Area sampled (m ²)	Sampling method	Habitat	Foundation species at the surface
SG197	EX6	0,16	Suction ultrafine	Surface	M
SG198	EX6	0,16	Suction ultrafine	Surface	M
SG199	EX6	0,16	Suction fine	Surface	M
SG200	EX6	0,16	Suction fine	Surface	M
SG210	EX6	0,16	Grab of mussels	Surface	M
SG201	EX6	0,06	Blue bag	Subseafloor	M
SG202	EX6	0,06	Suction	Subseafloor	M
SG203	EX6	0,06	Rocks	Subseafloor	M
SG204	EX6	0,06	Rocks	Subseafloor	M

Table 4. Preliminary results of diversity per habitat and experiment (EX). Abundance counts of macrofauna (over 1 mm; GA Gastropoda, BI Bivalvia, PO Polychaeta, CR Crustacea, O others), meiofauna (below 1 mm; CO Copepoda, NE Nematoda, O others; permanent vs non-permanent larvae/juveniles of GA Gastropoda + BI Bivalvia, PO Polychaeta) at higher taxonomic levels, as numbers will change with ongoing work (numbers updated on 04.07.2025). "Others" include less frequent high taxonomic ranks.

<i>Habitat</i>	<i>Macrofauna</i>						<i>Meiofauna (permanent)</i>			<i>Meiofauna (non-permanent)</i>	
	<i>Site</i>	<i>GA</i>	<i>BI</i>	<i>PO</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>CO</i>	<i>NE</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>GA + BI</i>	<i>PO</i>
Surface	EX 1	109	0	126	3	0	113	3	21	44	43
Surface	EX 2	1290	10	807	30	28	1493	3473	58	1080	1117
Surface	EX 3	176	1	214	2	3	195	1107	62	282	193
Surface	EX 4	28	0	29	7	1	144	273	19	36	88
Surface	EX 5	72	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Surface	EX 6	178	0	116	5	1	4	0	1	2	3
Total Surface		1853	11	1299	47	33	1949	4856	161	1444	1444
Subseafloor	EX 1	166	0	68	2	2	100	7	49	64	53
Subseafloor	EX 2	28	1	19	5	1	54	29	22	27	39
Subseafloor	EX 3	113	0	138	9	6	2014	81	114	14	29
Subseafloor	EX 4	25	2	44	1	1	217	2	40	6	29
Subseafloor	EX 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Subseafloor	EX 6	3	0	6	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
Total Subseafloor		335	3	275	19	10	2385	119	225	111	152
Basalt	EX 1	3	1	2	0	0	70	7	10	2	1
Basalt	EX 2	14	4	38	7	0	21	2	113	1	4

Basalt	EX 3	0	1	0	1	1	86	3	98	12	54
Total Basalt		17	6	40	8	1	177	12	221	15	59

Table 5. Overview of microbial samples collected during the research cruise, including sequencing code (Seq code), details of site (EX experiment), Habitat (Bas Basalt, Surf Surface, Sub Subseafloor), Foundation species found at Surface (Surf), M sampling method (filter, swab), and current status of the microbial community sequencing (green done, orange in progress at the time of report publication) of B bacteria, A archaea, E eukaryotes, F fungi.

Dive	Sample ID	Date Time	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)	Seq Code	Site	Habitat	Surface	M	16S B	16S A	18S E	IT S F
S0543	S0543_001	2023-07-04T17:55:34.910Z	9,84031	-104,291886	2517,08	F2446	EX 1	Bas	NA	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0543	S0543_001	2023-07-04T17:55:34.910Z	984031	-104291886	2517.08	F2447	EX 1	Bas	NA	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0543	S0543_001	2023-07-04T17:55:34.910Z	984031	-104291886	2517.08	F2448	EX 1	Bas	NA	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0544	S0544_010	2023-07-05T16:10:22.529Z	9,840238	-104,29178	2514,24	F2489	EX 1	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0544	S0544_010	2023-07-05T16:10:22.529Z	9840238	-10429178	2514.24	F2490	EX 1	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0544	S0544_010	2023-07-05T16:10:22.529Z	9840238	-10429178	2514.24	F2491	EX 1	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0546	S0546_025	2023-07-07T16:48:25.529Z	9,840181	-104,291815	2518,14	F2571	EX 2	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0546	S0546_025	2023-07-07T16:48:25.529Z	9840181	-104291815	2518.14	F2572	EX 2	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0546	S0546_025	2023-07-07T16:48:25.529Z	9840181	-104291815	2518.14	F2573	EX 2	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0548	S0548_038	2023-07-09T16:56:17.529Z	9,840139	-104,291748	2515,45	F2628	EX 3	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0548	S0548_038	2023-07-09T16:56:17.529Z	9,840139	-104,291748	2515,45	F2629	EX 3	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0548	S0548_038	2023-07-09T16:56:17.529Z	9,840139	-104,291748	2515,45	F2630	EX 3	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0550	S0550_056	2023-07-11T17:19:05.529Z	9,840225	-104,291746	2515,86	F2710	EX 2	Bas	NA	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0550	S0550_056	2023-07-11T17:19:05.529Z	9840225	-104291746	2515.86	F2711	EX 2	Bas	NA	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0550	S0550_056	2023-07-11T17:19:05.529Z	9840225	-104291746	2515.86	F2712	EX 2	Bas	NA	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0552	S0552_089	2023-07-13T17:35:32.119Z	9,840203	-104,291862	2514,29	F2802	EX 1	Surf	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0553	S0553_097	2023-07-14T17:57:01.214Z	9,840169	-104,291826	2514,32	F2877	EX 1	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0553	S0553_097	2023-07-14T17:57:01.214Z	9840169	-104291826	2514.32	F2878	EX 1	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0553	S0553_097	2023-07-14T17:57:01.214Z	9840169	-104291826	2514.32	F2879	EX 1	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0555	S0555_131	2023-07-16T16:43:26.751Z	9,840102	-104,291809	2515,31	F2952	EX 2	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0555	S0555_131	2023-07-16T16:43:26.751Z	9840102	-104291809	2515.31	F2953	EX 2	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0555	S0555_131	2023-07-16T16:43:26.751Z	9840102	-104291809	2515.31	F2954	EX 2	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0556	S0556_152	2023-07-17T16:48:48.202Z	9,840091	-104,291749	2516,22	F2996	EX 3	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0556	S0556_152	2023-07-17T16:48:48.202Z	9840091	-104291749	2516.22	F3031	EX 4	Sub	TW	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0558	S0558_181	2023-07-19T18:52:15.238Z	9,840157	-104,291797	2516,04	F3077	EX 5	Sub	M	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0558	S0558_181	2023-07-19T18:52:15.238Z	9840157	-104291797	2516.04	F3078	EX 5	Sub	M	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0558	S0558_181	2023-07-19T18:52:15.238Z	9840157	-104291797	2516.04	F3079	EX 5	Sub	M	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0560	S0560-209	2023-07-21T16:19:19.522Z	9840077	-104291807	2515,52	F3146	EX 6	Sub	M	Filter	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
S0543	S0543_002	2023-07-04T19:07:41.910Z	9,840317	-104,291879	2517,13	S2449	EX 1	Bas	NA	Swab	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange

Dive	Sample ID	Date Time	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)	Seq Code	Site	Habitat	Surface	M	16S B	16S A	18S E	ITS F
S0544	S0544_014	2023-07-05T17:15:58.529Z	9,840238	-104,291777	2515,6	S2510	EX 1	Surf	TW	Swab				
S0548	S0548_041	2023-07-09T19:16:48.529Z	9,840097	-104,291756	2515,3	S2626	EX 3	Surf	TW	Swab				
S0550	S0550_056	2023-07-11T17:19:05.529Z	9,840225	-104,291746	2515,86	S2709	EX 2	Bas	NA	Swab				
S0553	S0553_104	2023-07-14T19:25:45.687Z	9,840158	-104,291874	2514,37	S2830	EX 1	Sub	TW	Swab				
S0554	S0554_112	2023-07-15T15:55:50.690Z	9,840122	-104,291819	2513,89	S2909	EX 2	Surf	TW	Swab				
S0554	S0554_112	2023-07-15T15:55:50.690Z	9,840122	-104,291819	2513,89	S2910	EX 2	Sub	TW	Swab				
S0555	S0555_139	2023-07-16T19:56:54.224Z	9,840193	-104,291925	2511,28	S2955	EX 3	Bas	NA	Swab				
S0556	S0556_156	2023-07-17T20:24:25.003Z	9,840097	-104,29179	2515,37	S3002	EX 3	Sub	TW	Swab				
S0557	S0557_165	2023-07-18T16:25:09.823Z	9,84013	-104,291842	2515,41	S3034	EX 4	Sub	TW	Swab				
S0557	S0557_165	2023-07-18T16:25:09.823Z	9,84013	-104,291842	2515,41	S3035	EX 4	Surf	TW	Swab				
S0558	S0558_182	2023-07-19T20:06:44.509Z	9,84016	-104,291807	2515,92	S3075	EX 5	Surf	M	Swab				
S0558	S0558_182	2023-07-19T20:06:44.509Z	9,84016	-104,291807	2515,92	S3076	EX 5	Sub	M	Swab				
S0560	S0560_211	2023-07-21T16:19:19.522Z	9,840077	-104,291807	2515,52	S3144	EX 6	Surf	M	Swab				
S0560	S0560_211	2023-07-21T16:19:19.522Z	9,840077	-104,291807	2515,52	S3145	EX 6	Sub	M	Swab				

Table 6. Barcoding of macro- and meiofauna for taxonomic assignment. Information on the sample from which individuals were retrieved is provided, as well as the sequence length of cytochrome c oxidase subunit I, and taxonomic assignment.

Sub sample ID	Site	Habitat	Individual code name	Sequence length (bp)	Taxonomic assignment
SG153			153-4-1	477	Polychaeta n. sp. 1
SG153			153-4-3	508	Polychaeta n. sp. 1
SG035			035cil1	517	Polychaeta n. sp. 1
SG035	EX 2	Surface	035cil2	508	<i>Riftia pachyptila</i> larva
SG035	EX 2	Surface	035cil3	403	<i>Riftia pachyptila</i> larva
SG035	EX 2	Surface	035cil4	501	<i>Riftia pachyptila</i> larva
SG035	EX 2	Surface	035cil5	500	<i>Riftia pachyptila</i> larva
SG035	EX 2	Surface	035pol1	508	<i>Amphisamytha galapagensis</i>
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-1	525	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i> (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-2	522	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i>
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-3	499	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i> (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-4	481	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i> (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-5	513	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i> (Clade 2)

Sub sample ID	Site	Habitat	Individual code name	Sequence length (bp)	Taxonomic assignment
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-6	495	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-7	518	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-8	457	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-10	515	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-11	514	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-12	499	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-13	511	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-14	502	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-15	498	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-16	499	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-17	498	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-18	516	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-19	521	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-20	499	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-21	512	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-22	514	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-23	515	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-24	515	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-25	497	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-26	500	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-27	515	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-28	497	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-29	511	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG034	EX 2	Surface	Lele-34-2-30	513	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-1	626	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-2	620	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-3	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-4	627	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-5	627	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-6	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-7	635	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-8	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-9	627	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-10	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-11	618	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-12	626	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-13	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-14	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)

Sub sample ID	Site	Habitat	Individual code name	Sequence length (bp)	Taxonomic assignment
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-15	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-16	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-17	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-18	620	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-19	620	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-20	618	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-21	617	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-22	620	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-23	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-24	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-25	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-26	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-27	636	<i>Lepetodrilus pustulosus</i>
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-28	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-29	616	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG167	EX 3	Subseafloor	Lele-167-30	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-1	638	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-2	636	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-3	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-4	637	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-5	636	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-8	636	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-9	636	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-10	636	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-11	636	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-12	636	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-79-13	636	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-144-1	638	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-144-2	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-144-3	615	<i>Lepetodrilus pustulosus</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-144-4	619	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i>
SG079	EX 1	Subseafloor	juv-172-2	637	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG185	EX 5	Subseafloor	Lele-185-1	642	<i>Lepetodrilus ovalis</i>
SG185	EX 5	Subseafloor	Lele-185-2	639	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG185	EX 5	Subseafloor	Lele-185-3	642	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG185	EX 5	Subseafloor	Lele-185-4	641	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG185	EX 5	Subseafloor	Lele-185-5	640	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_2	633	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)

Sub sample ID	Site	Habitat	Individual code name	Sequence length (bp)	Taxonomic assignment
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_3	610	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_4	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_5	558	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_8	625	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_10	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_11	628	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_13	640	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_16	612	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_17	638	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_18	629	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_20	624	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_21	564	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_24	635	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG076	NA	Crab Spa	Lele_Crab_25	626	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-1	625	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-3	622	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-4	653	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-5	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-6	611	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i>
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-7	640	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-8	635	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-9	635	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-10	664	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-11	627	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-12	618	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-13	618	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-14	623	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-15	641	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-16	633	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-17	632	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-18	637	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-19	620	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-20	633	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-22	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-23	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-24	611	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG066	NA	BioVent	Lele-BioV-25	634	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)

Sub sample ID	Site	Habitat	Individual code name	Sequence length (bp)	Taxonomic assignment
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-1	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-2	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-3	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-4	635	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-5	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-6	638	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-7	637	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-8	639	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-9	634	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-10	635	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-11	649	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-12	621	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-13	629	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-14	559	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-16	627	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-17	636	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-18	639	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-19	642	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-20	626	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-21	638	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-22	634	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-23	634	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 2)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-24	635	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)
SG028	NA	Bioshop Spire	Lele-Bios-25	625	Lepetodrilus elevatus (Clade 1)

3.2 Science Party Information

Table 7. List of scientists and students aboard Falkor (too).

Scientist	Institution
Monika Bright	University of Vienna
Salvador Manuel Espada-Hinojosa	University of Vienna
Avery Fulford	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Sabine Gollner	Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)
Stéphane Hourdez	Observatoire Océanologique de Banyuls
Ian Hughes	Harvard University
Clarissa Karthäuser	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Ingrid Kolar	University of Vienna
Nicole Krause	University of Vienna
Victor Le Layec	Independent
Tihomir Makovec	NIB Marine Biological Station Piran (MBSP)
Alessandro Messori	Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)
Jessica Mitchell	Harvard University
André Luiz de Oliveira	Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology
Philipp Pröts	University of Vienna
Ivonne Rodriguez	University Of Costa Rica
Fanny Sieler	Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)
Stefan Sievert	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Jan Steger	University of Vienna
Tinkara Tinta	NIB Marine Biological Station Piran (MBSP)
Teresa Winter	University of Vienna

3.3 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

Oral Presentations

Sabine Gollner, Monika Bright, André Luiz de Oliveira, Salvador Espada-Hinojosa, Avery Fulford, Ian Vincent Hughes, Stéphane Hourdez, Clarissa Karthäuser, Ingrid Kolar, Nicole Krause, Victor Le Layec, Tihomir Makovec, Alessandro Messori, Jessica Mitchell, Philipp Pröts, Ivonne Rodríguez-Ramírez, Fanny Sieler, Stefan M. Sievert, Jan Steger, Tinkara Tinta, Teresa Rosa Maria Winter, Zach Bright, Russel Coffield, Carl Hill, Kris Ingram, Alex Paris (2025) Animal life in the shallow subseafloor crust at deep-sea hydrothermal vents. 17th Deep Sea Biology Symposium, Hong Kong

Lara Baptista, Jara Westbeek, Monika Bright, Sabine Gollner S. (2024). Uncovering hidden communities in deep-sea hydrothermal vent seafloor habitats. *NWO Life Conference 2024*, Egmond aan Zee, The Netherlands

Poster Presentations

Lara Baptista, Teresa Winter, Monika Bright, Sabine Gollner (2024). Animal life in the underworld of hydrothermal vents: preliminary insights. *NWO Life Conference 2024*, Egmond aan Zee, The Netherlands.

Lara Baptista, Jara Westbeek, Monika Bright, Sabine Gollner (2025). Subseafloor life at hydrothermal vents: macrofauna diversity and trait-analyses. *17th Deep Sea Biology Symposium*, Hong Kong.

3.4 Student Projects, Thesis, and Dissertations

Alessandro Messori (master student RUG, NL, project carried out at NIOZ, supervisor Gollner) Limits of Life: The Thermal Tolerance of Copepods in extreme environments, from Deep-sea Hydrothermal Vents to the Intertidal Zone (10/2023)

Jara Westbeek (master student Utrecht University, NL, project carried out at NIOZ, supervisor Gollner & Baptista): Animal biodiversity in cavities below deep-sea hydrothermal vents and connectivity to seafloor habitats (02/2025)

Finet Nelissen (student at AERES hooge school Almere, NL, final practical carried out at NIOZ, supervisor Gollner & Baptista; 06/2025)

Antonia Auer (master student University of Vienna), ongoing gene expression analyses of free-living *Candidatus* Endoriftia persephone, supervisor Bright

The following persons contributed to the sorting and identification of fauna under the supervision of Gollner: Dr. Lara Baptista (NIOZ, NL; employed post-doc dedicated to this project; co-supervisor of all students who worked in this project), Kjeld Werther (bachelor student, NIOZ & UU, NL; ongoing), Hein Hermans (bachelor student, NIOZ & UU, NL; ongoing), Levi Davids (master student NIOZ & RUG, NL; ongoing)

3.5 Cruise Records

- [Cruise Logs](#).
- [ROV SuBastian Dive list](#).

3.6 Media

Radio: Bright at Austrian public radio Ö1: under Pressure: Extremisten in der Tiefsee (1.3.2023)

Radio: Gollner at Dutch national radio: NPO1 spraakmakers (28.08.2023)

Radio: Gollner at Dutch national radio: NPO1, nieuws & co(20.09.2024)

TV: Gollner at Dutch national TV: NOS, 8 uur journal (20.09.2024)

TV: Bright at Austrian national TV: Puls 4 7.00 (21.10.2024)

Radio: Baptista at Portuguese radiostreams and publications at the respective websites: Rádio Comercial, Cidade FM, M80, Smooth FM (28.10.2025)

3.7 Community Outreach

Talk Bright (27.9.2023): Rahlgasse AUT, Wien: Die Unterwelt der Hydrothermalquellen (reach: ~200 children)

Talk Bright (7.11.2023): Marine Biology Station Piran, Slovenia: The Underworld of Hydrothermal vents (reach ~100 citizens and scientists)

Talk Gollner (14.11 2023): Naturalis (NL, Leiden): Spotlight Diepzee geheimen (reach: ~80 citizens)

Talk Gollner (12.3.2024): IVN (NL, Texel): De Diepzee - bron van Leven! (reach: ~100 citizens)

Talk Bright (8.6.2024): Science for the Public in the country, Austrian Academy of Science, Lofer: Forschung in der Tiefsee: Leben in der Unterwelt der Thermalquellen am Pazifischen Feuerring (reach: ~100 citizens)

Talk: Gollner (21.11.2024) EMB Third Thursday Science Webinar, 21 Nov 2024; Discovery of animal life in the ocean's crust at deep-sea hydrothermal vents: implications for future research and management (reach: >6.6 K views on you tube)

Talk: Gollner (18.03.2025) DOSI Side Event, Kingston, Jamaica (ISA council): The discovery of animal life in earth's crust below deep-sea hydrothermal vents and implications for ABMTs (reach: ~100 delegates of the International Seabed Authority)

Talk: Gollner (28.04.2025) Public talk in Sierning, Austria: Wunder der Tiefsee (reach: >100 citizens)

Talk: Baptista (08.06.2025): Public talk in the Naturalis Biodiversity Center, The Netherlands, during the World Ocean Day celebrations: Leven 2500 meters onder de zee~ / Life 2500 meters under the sea (reach: ~50 citizens)

3.7.1. Additional outreach activities

Life in the cracks of the crust

More than 40 years ago the discovery of hydrothermal vents in the calderas of the earth's longest mountain range in the Pacific Ocean was a scientific sensation! Completely independent of sunlight, hidden in depths of more than 2000 meters, specific bacteria fix carbon dioxide to produce energy for life. This organic material is the food source for a bizarre and unique fauna. Giant tubeworms lacking a gut, thousands of shrimps swarming around the hot chimneys, or mussels piling up meters high in crumple space, are just a few examples of this fauna. In the past as well today the fascination with this habitat, which holds countless secrets, is ongoing.

Scientists realize that life exists also below the seafloor of hydrothermal vents. The habitat is even less studied. In the cracks of the Earth's crust a few bacteria and archaea have been found. But what is with animals? Virtually nothing is known. There might be some hiding there or using the path of water flow through the crust to emerge at vents to settle. This is why we set out to discover life below vents. We plan to characterize subsurface biosphere diversity, from viruses to animals, at deep-sea hydrothermal vents to elucidate the nature and extent of connectivity between the surface and subsurface biospheres. Consistent with SOI's mission, we will expand our knowledge of limits of eukaryotic life during a three-week cruise with R/V Falkor and ROV SuBastian to East Pacific Rise vents at the 9°50'N region currently scheduled for summer 2023.

The aim of **LCC – Life in the Cracks of the Crust** is to awaken the curiosity of students with an interactive, multidisciplinary, multilingual program and to share the knowledge of the earth's largest habitat – the deep-sea hot vents and subsurface of the Earth. LCC will offer the virtual participation of schools during the next cruise in summer 2023. We will assist the children in the development of experiments carried out with the ROV during the cruise with telepresence, public documentation and presentation of exciting results during and after the cruise. Activities in English, German, Dutch, Slovenian, Portuguese and Spanish, which will be available here.

Vent animals – Meat Munchers or Leaf Lovers?

Class 5A (14 – 15 years old students, teacher Ulrike Randl-Gadora), AHS Rahlgasse, Vienna, Austria

Background: The animals living at the deep-sea hydrothermal vents of the volcano of the East Pacific Rise are well known. About 50 species bristle worms (Phylum Annelida, family Polychaeta), snails (Phylum Mollusca, family Gastropoda), a few mussels and clams (Phylum Mollusca, family Bivalvia) and a few crustaceans (Phylum Arthropoda, family Crustacea) are described in Desbruyeres D., Segonzac M., Bright M. 2006. Handbook of Deep-Sea Hydrothermal Vent Fauna. 2nd edition. Denisia 18, Landesmuseum Linz, Austria pp. 554. The diet of the vent animals is based on chemosynthesis. Some animals graze over the surfaces to feed on these chemosynthetic bacteria, other are filter feeder and collect the bacteria from the water. There are a lot of predators feeding on animals or scavengers feeding on dead animals. Others apparently are not picky and feed on dead and alive animals. Because of the lack of light in the deep sea, however, no plants live in the deep sea. Therefore, we expect animals are carnivores rather than vegetarians because this is the food they know. Further we believe that animals will prefer fat and proteins over carbohydrates, simply because animal carbohydrates are rather rare. Since proteins are mainly used as building blocks in metabolism and are only broken down as energy supply when carbohydrates and fat can no longer be metabolized, we assume that animals also prefer fat (even when we humans would rather eat a steak than a piece of pork fat). Ultimately, the closer the food is the faster they will find it, not with their eyes (which are useless in the dark) but by smell.

Hypothesis 1: We hypothesize that vent animals will prefer meat over plants.

Hypothesis 2: We hypothesize that vent animals prefer fats over proteins over carbohydrates.

Hypothesis 3: We hypothesize that vent animals will find food faster the closer it is.

Material and Methods: We use two kitchen oven grids and place on each three animal and three plant products on the grid and secure them with cable ties. On each corner of the oven grid, a 0.5 kg lead weight is mounted. We further use a labelled plastic bucket lid (already prepared in Vienna). The lid is secured with ropes to the grid prior deployment. Kitchen oven grid, lead, rope and buckets lids will be shipped from Vienna to Costa Rica.

Somewhere in the 14 boxes shipped from Vienna to Costa Rica are the items for this experiment.

Shopping tour in Costa Rica

Prior the research cruise scientists bought the following meat and veggies: fat, liver, nuts, chickpeas and potatoes. In addition, they also collected a net from the side of the road to use for mounting the food items on the kitchen grid.

Kitchen oven grids and scuba diving lead

Labelled bucket lids

The following food items will be bought in Puntarenas, Costa Rica prior boarding the ship and stored in a refrigerator until the deployment: Animal pig rind (fat), muscle meat (protein), liver (carbohydrate), plant coconut fat or brazil nuts (fat), lentils or beans (protein), potato (carbohydrate).

Prior deployment in the crater of the volcano at 2500 m depth, the two grids with the food will be secured on the platform of the ROV SuBastian. One grid will be deployed in a vent area with a lot of animals, the other one on bare basalt a few meters away. Deployment will be filmed and still pictures will be taken. The plan is to visit this site a few hours after deployment and during the next days. The end of the experiments depends on 1) how fast animal find the food and eat it and 2) how often it will be possible to visit this deployment. At the end the scientists will use the multi-chamber suction sampler on the ROV to collect all animals on each food item separately. In the lab onboard the ship the animals will be fixed in ethanol and shipped back to Vienna for counting of animals and identification of animal species by the students of the 5A class.

Shopping tour in Costa Rica

Prior the research cruise in July 2023 scientists bought the following meat and veggies: fat, liver, nuts, chickpeas and potatoes. In addition, they also collected a net from the side of the road to use for mounting the food items on the kitchen grid.

The search for food and net

Mounting of experiments

On board the ship, the food was mounted on the kitchen grid together with the markers from the school and some diving lead for adding weight. This happened very early in the morning prior deployment.

Work early in the morning to mount the food prior deployment

Travel to the depths of the Pacific Ocean

Finally, we brought the food in the crater of the volcano in about 2500 m depth. One deployment was on bare basalt with no visible animals present, the other one in the middle of warm vent with lots of animals.

Transport and deployment of experiments with ROV SuBastian, dive 548

3 hours after the deployment (548) the ROV re-visited the experiments for the first observation. Further visits were executed during the following 7 days except for day 1 and day 6 where we did not manage to visit.

Dive 548 – left side bare basalt, right side warm vent

Analyses in Vienna

The students from the Rahlgasse then received then photos of the videos at the start of the new semester in September 2023. The identification of the animals was conducted by Monika Bright. The data analysis is based on the photos. The first photos (Day 0, dive 548) date three hours after the deployment of the grids at the two locations (basalt, deep-sea vent), with all subsequent photos taken at approximately the same time on the following days. There are no photos for Day 1 and Day 6. In total, five days were evaluated based on multiple photos per day: Day 0 (548), Days 2 to 5 (550 to 553), and Day 7 (555). For clarity, the missing days (highlighted in gray) are also included in the data table.

Individuals were counted only if they touched the grid with the food offerings. Merely orienting towards the grid without touching it was not sufficient for counting purposes. If photos of a particular day showed different numbers of individuals of a species, the highest count was used. If the mouthparts of an individual were on a food source (fat, meat, liver, nuts, chickpeas, potatoes), it was assigned to that source. If this was not possible, the individual was counted as "Grid".

The winner is the squat lobster *Munidopsis*

Most often, the squat lobster of the genus *Munidopsis* was encountered, which is why in Table 1 only the number of individuals (without letters for the genus) is given. Identification at the species level was not possible here. The other two species, the crabs *Bythogrea thermydron* and *Cyanagrea praedator*, were each represented by only one individual and were therefore marked in the table without a count, but with the initial letter of their genus (B; C).

Time		Basalt								Vent							
Day (dive)	+	F E	F L	LE	N	K	E	G	Σ	F E	F L	L E	N	K	E	G	Σ
0 (548)	3 h	1		1, B		1		1	4, B								0
1 (549)	1 d																
2 (550)	2 d	2	3	2					7			Q					Q

Time		Basalt							Vent								
3 (551)	3 d		2	2	1			3	8			Q					Q
4 (552)	4 d	1	1	1			1	2	6		C	Q					Q, C
5 (553)	5 d	1	2	2		1		1	7			Q					Q
6 (554)	6 d																
7 (555)	7 d	1	1	1		1	1		5			Q					Q
Σ		6	9	9, B	1	3	2	7	38	0	1	Q	0	0	0	0	Q

Raw Data and abbreviations

- FE Fat, FL Meat, LE Liver (animal food sources highlighted in red)
- N Nuts, K Chickpeas, E Potato (plant-based food sources highlighted in green)
- G Grid. Q No data available due to loss of liver. ©U. Randl-Gadora, E. Wiederhold

A total of 39 animals were counted at both sites combined, with 97.43% on basalt and 2.56% at the vent. 36 animals belong to the genus *Munidopsis*, accounting for 94.87%, exclusively present on basalt. Considering the occurrence of all 36 counted individuals of *Munidopsis* over the entire study period, a classic succession pattern emerges with few individuals at the beginning, many in the middle, and few at the end of the experiment (Fig. 1). This pattern approximates a normal distribution.

Photograph of *Munidopsis* spp. left side, dive 548 left side, distribution of counted individuals of *Munidopsis* spp. during the study period

One individual of the crab *Bythogrea thermydron* was found on basalt. Another single individual of the crab *Cyanagrea praedator* was detected at the vent site.

The rarely detected crabs *Cyanagrea praedator* from the vent, left side and *Bythogrea thermydron* from basalt, right side

Who ate the liver at the vent site?

Between the first and second photoshoots, the animal carbohydrate source was completely removed. It can be assumed that a large animal, likely a shark, a large bony fish, or an octopus, was responsible for this. However, since there are no photos of this event, this assumption cannot be proven.

Photograph of liver at vent site 3 hours after deployment left side and same area of liver 2 days after deployment right side, see yellow arrows

When natural food is plenty, foreign food is not attractive

Since only a single animal was detected at the vent, the hypothesis that animals living near a deep-sea vent find or explore new food sources more quickly than animals living on bare basalt far from deep-sea vents is falsified. It is plausible that vent-dwelling animals have no incentive to seek out new food sources as long as sufficient natural food is available. It can be assumed that competition for food in the vicinity of a deep-sea vent only increases when the food supply diminishes.

Photograph vent site experiment, dive 555 lacking animals interested in the foreign food

When food is scarce, foreign food is attractive

The bare basalt is an environment perceived “empty” to do the scarcity of large animals. This environment is also known to offer little natural food. Therefore, a new food source like our experimental food is attractive. Many animals were found directly sitting or feeding on the experimental food but also were seen in the vicinity of the experiment. It is likely perceived through olfactory cues. However, the extent to which competition for this food increases over time could not be investigated in this experiment.

Photograph of basalt site experiment, dive 553 (Note that there was also another experiment conducted at this site.)

***Munidopsis* prefers to feed on what it knows**

Overall, animal food sources were visited 80.6% of the time, by an average of 4 animals per day, while plant food sources were visited approximately 19.4% of the time, by one animal per day. A comparison between animal and plant food sources clearly demonstrates a preference for the

former. Thus, the hypothesis that deep-sea animals prefer animal food over plant food can be verified.

Comparison of the preference of animal and plant food sources, left side ©U. Randl-Gadora; right animals on meat, fat and liver as well as on potato and chickpeas, dive 555

***Munidopsis* is on a high-carbohydrate diet**

Fat sources were visited by only about 22% of individuals throughout the study period, while protein sources were visited by approximately 38%, with a greater range of variation. On average, carbohydrate sources were slightly more attractive than protein sources, at around 40%. This result seems to refute the hypothesis that fats are preferred over proteins and proteins over carbohydrates. Carbohydrates appear to be the most attractive, closely followed by proteins, with fats being the least attractive.

To verify whether the preference for carbohydrates applies equally to both animal and plant sources, we compared the animal and plant nutrients. It is evident that in both cases, fatty food sources exhibit the lowest preference. However, unlike animal sources, protein sources are preferred in the plant-based food offerings.

It should be noted that no feeding traces were detected on the potato and nuts, and the surface of the swollen and pre-cooked chickpeas did not provide clear indications. Therefore, it is questionable whether mere contact of mouthparts with a food source justifies the counting mentioned earlier. Detailed video recordings of at least five to ten minutes per individual and microscopic examinations of the surfaces would be necessary to clarify which food source is visited by which animal species and for how long, as well as whether an individual actually feeds there. It is recommended to take additional close-up photos and videos for a more precise evaluation to assess details sharply. Taking animals for an analysis of their stomach contents is not feasible for ethical reasons.

It should be noted that no feeding traces were found on the potatoes and nuts, and the surface of the soaked and precooked chickpeas also did not provide any clear evidence. Therefore, it is questionable whether mere contact of the mouthparts with a food source justifies the aforementioned count. Detailed video recordings of at least five to ten minutes per individual and microscopic examinations of the surfaces would be necessary to clarify which food source is visited by which animal species, for how long, and whether an individual actually feeds there. For a more precise evaluation, it is recommended to take additional close-ups and videos to be able to assess details clearly. Removing animals for analysis of their stomach contents is not advisable for ethical reasons.

Preference of protein, carbohydrates and fat of animal and plant food sources. ©U. Randl-Gadora

What can be done better in future?

It cannot be ruled out that the consistency of the food offerings had a significant influence on the results. The potato should not have been raw but cooked. The substantial difference between the fat sources used (nuts and bacon rind) could be minimized by using a package of plant-based butter or coconut fat instead of the nuts and a package of cow milk butter instead of the bacon rind.

At the same time, it is essential to offer all food sources in the same manner. Instead of just packing small items like nuts or chickpeas into a net, the larger food sources (bacon rind, liver, meat, potato) could be cut into nut-sized pieces and should also be packed in a net.

Further is worth considering not offering all food sources directly, but rather through a kind of bird feeder, where the food is contained in a transparent silo and pushed downward through gravity to an opening. This eliminates the need for using a net, as the food pieces should easily slide downward. This could be ensured by using kitchen scale weights placed on a loose cover plate above the food. However, the feeder must be tested underwater beforehand for its suitability, including ensuring good accessibility of the food for the animals. It is recommended to attach horizontal lines to the feeder silo to easily read the daily change in volume. For safety, these lines should be engraved and additionally marked with color, for example, using a white marker.

Magic Beans in the Deep Sea

Elementary School Ciril Kosmač Piran (7 – 8 year old students, teachers Vika Kuštrin) Piran, Slovenia in collaboration with Marine Biology Station Piran, National Institute of Biology and their IOC UNESCO activities

In the famous fairy tale magic beans grow into a huge beanstalk reaching to the clouds (Jack and the Beanstalk). Let's see if our beans do the same at the bottom of the ocean.

Background:

We know that sprouting of bean seeds takes about a week. You either can put them directly in the soil or you can also put them between layers of paper and moist the paper. Then they will sprout but only at warm temperature, therefore seed should not sprout when it is too cold. It takes about a week for beans to sprout.

On March 16, 2011 the ship MS Oliva ran aground on Nightingale Island in the Atlantic Ocean. After all crew members were rescued, the ship broke up a few days later. The cargo was 60.000 tons of soy beans. Lots of oil was spilled into the ocean creating sever environmental damage. Beans were also spilled into the ocean but what happened to them was not further described. Six months later divers found rotten away bean areas in the ship wreck.

It is unknown whether beans can sprout in seawater. We also do not know if they sprout at high pressure in the deep sea.

Hypothesis: Beans will not sprout in cold, deep-sea water but will sprout in warm deep-sea water

Material and Methods: We will put beans between layers of paper and then place them in bags made out of panty hoses. For the deployment with the ROV we will mount a scuba diving lead on this bag with a rope, and to find the bag we will mount a lid of a plastic bucket on a second rope. Two of these bags will be deployed, one in warm vent water and one in a cold area. We will leave the bags in the deep sea for about 10 days. As control we also will put beans between layers of paper – moist them either with seawater or with freshwater and leave them at warm temperature in the lab. Another set we will put in the refrigerator.

Let's see what happens with the beans in the deep sea and compare them to the beans in the lab.

On board we first repeated the experiments conducted by Elementary School Cirila Kosmača Piran on land. We exposed mixture of beans to freshwater and seawater and incubated them at room temperature or at 4°C in the dark and followed any signs of sprouting daily. We found out that only beans exposed to freshwater sprouted: first the ones at room temperature, but few days later also some from the batch incubated at 4°C. On the other hand, beans exposed to seawater did not show any sign of sprouting. Even more so, beans exposed to seawater at room temperature were covered in mold after 10 days.

(Top left) The four on board bean sprouting treatments (fresh and salt water, cold and room temperature). (Center left) Room temperature fresh water beans sprouted. (Center right) Room temperature salt water beans did not sprout, and grew some fungi. (Top right) Cold temperature salt water beans did not sprout either.

Next, we wrapped two batches of beans in two different bags with pores that allowed for water exchange and prepared them for the dive with ROV SuBastian from the Schmidt Ocean Institute.

(Top left) We use a mesh to wrap the beans. (Center left) They got wrapped in a bag. (Center right) Bean bag deployed in the deep ocean. (Top right) Bean bags back on board after recovery

They dived all the way through the water column, down to 2500 m depth, where we placed one bag in the vicinity of hydrothermal vent and the other away from it.

(Left) School experiments in the deep sea. (Center) SuBastian deploying the bag of beans. (Right) Bag of beans and the weight attached to it

We followed what was happening for the next 7 days. In fact, animals at the sea floor did not really care about the beans, so we brought them back to surface afterwards and repeated the experiment in the laboratory. We again exposed beans to freshwater and seawater and kept them at room temperature or at 4°C in the dark and followed any signs of sprouting daily. What happened? Again, unfortunately our beans did not like to journey so much as none of them

showed any signs of sprouting. So, either beans were not magical or seawater and high pressure are not good conditions to cultivate your beans.

(Left) Beans from the depth. (Center) Once we opened the bag of beans. (Right) Salvador Espada and Tinkara Tinta

BARBARASCHOOL

Elementary School [Barbaraschool](#) (10 – 11-year-old students, teacher Isabel Spruijt) Bunnik, Netherlands in collaboration with the [Royal Netherlands Institute for Marine Research \(NIOZ\)](#)

Under pressure!

Background:

Our bodies are adapted to the atmospheric pressure on Earth which is one 1 bar at sea level. You may have experienced a change of this pressure when you are sitting in an airplane and feel a “plop” in your ears as the pressure of the air on your inner ear decreases when you ascend. When you jump into a swimming pool and dive to the bottom of the pool, the pressure increases with water depth and you can also feel this as your ears might start hurting as the water pushes against your inner ear.

In the sea, the pressure increases with 1 bar every 10 meters, which is a lot, as the water is much heavier than the air. Animals that live in the deep sea are adapted to this enormous pressure. When we perform our scientific experiments in the deep sea with submersibles or robots, the

materials need to be strong enough to resist the pressure of the water. But how strong are the materials? What happens with “daily life” materials when they are exposed to the depths of our ocean?

Hypothesis: Materials that are filled with air are destroyed as the water pressure compacts them. Materials that are solid stay intact because they are not compressed by the water pressure.

Material and Methods: We thought about daily life materials where we want to know what happens with them under water pressure. The materials we want to test are: an air-filled balloon, a ping-pong ball, a raw egg, a cooked egg, pasta, eatable gummybears and marshmallows.

We want to mount these materials on the ROV platform and film it with the camera of the ROV while it is descending to 2500 meters water depth. Let’s see what happens!

At sea: During the expedition the selected items were placed into a plastic container that allowed exchange with water and pressure. The air-filled balloon very quickly shrank, the ping-pong ball plopped, nothing visible happened to the eggs (the egg shell can let water through via its pores), or to the pasta; the gummybears became a bit more soft as they were exposed to water, and the marshmallow shrank a bit and also dissolved a bit. The video and pictures were shared with the kids (Figure X).

Chef cook in the deep sea

Background: The fluids of the hydrothermal vents can reach really high temperatures, especially at the black smokers, where temperatures of above 300 degree Celsius can be measured.

Hypothesis: You can cook an egg or pasta or marshmallow in the hot vent fluids.

Material and Methods: In the first experiment we want to find out if an uncooked egg, marshmallows and pasta can resist the great pressure. If yes, we place the food into a steel-mesh that is mounted on a steel handle. The ROV-manipulator is then holding the steel-handle with the attached steel-mesh that is filled with the food for 10 minutes into hot vent fluids. Back on board of the ship, we will open the egg and taste the marshmallow and pasta if it they are well cooked. Enjoy!

At sea: We decided to cook the egg for a few minutes. It very quickly turned black, due tot the iron-metals in the vent fluids of the black smoker. On board we broke the egg and – had a perfect soft-cooked egg!

Photographs of experiments planned by the Barbara School kids